

Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020

*Bordered Magic Square of Order
20 with magic sum 2020
For a day 20 of each month of 2020*

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*The idea of **bordered magic squares** is well known in the literature. In this work, **bordered magic squares** are constructed in such a way that the final magic sum of each **bordered magic square** is 2020. The work is for the orders 3 to 25. In each case, a symmetric result is found for the magic sums of **sub-magic squares**. The work include fractional, decimal and whole numbers with positive and negative signs.*

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¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978–2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976–1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <https://inderjtaneja.com>; <https://indertaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; Instagram: @crazynumbers.

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1 Introduction

Based on the work of H. White [6], recently, author [10, 11, 12, 13, 14] worked on the **bordered magic squares** in different ways. Some of these ways are specified in following two subsections.

1.1 Odd Ordered Natural Number Entries

Author [12] studied the **bordered magic squares** for the **consecutive odd numbers**. The summary is given in the following result.

Result 1.1. [12] *For bordered magic squares for consecutive odd numbers, the total entries sums are given by*

$$T_{k \times m} := k^2 \times m^2,$$

*where k is the order of bordered magic squares, and m is the order of each bordered sub-magic square. This lead us to very interesting connection with **Pythagoras theorem**.*

In particular, the bordered magic squares constructed with odd order consecutive natural numbers starting from 1, the total sum entries are as follows:

- ▶ order 24, $k = 24$, $T_{24 \times m} := 24^2 \times m^2$, $m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22$ and 24;
- ▶ order 25, $k = 25$, $T_{25 \times m} := 25^2 \times m^2$, $m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23$ and 25.

1.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

Author [13] studied the **bordered magic squares** for the **consecutive natural numbers**. The summary is given in the following result.

Result 1.2. [13] *The bordered magic squares constructed for the consecutive natural numbers starting from 1 satisfy the following properties:*

- i. $S_{k \times k} := k \times L$;
- ii. $T_{k \times k} := k^2 \times L$;
- iii. $C_{k \times k} := (k - 1) \times 4 \times L$;
- iv. $d_{border} := 8 \times L$.

where k is the order of bordered magic square and

$$L := T_{1 \times 1}, \text{ odd order magic squares}$$

$$L := \frac{T_{2 \times 2}}{4}, \text{ even order magic squares}$$

and

- $S_{k \times k} \longrightarrow$ magic square sums;
- $T_{k \times k} \longrightarrow$ total entries sums;
- $C_{k \times k} \longrightarrow$ borders entries sums;
- $d_{border} \longrightarrow$ difference among borders value.

In particular, for the orders 24 and 25, we have

1. For the **bordered magic square** of order 24 for the consecutive entries 1 to 576, has the following symmetric results:

- i. $S_{k \times k} := \frac{k}{2} \times \frac{T_{2 \times 2}}{2}$;
- ii. $T_{k \times k} := \left(\frac{k}{2}\right)^2 \times T_{2 \times 2}$;
- iii. $C_{k \times k} := (k - 1) \times T_{2 \times 2}$.
- iv. $d_{border} := 2 \times T_{2 \times 2}$.

where $k = 4, 6, \dots, 20, 22$ and 24 orders of magic squares appearing **bordered magic square** of order 24, and $T_{2 \times 2} := 1154$ is the sum of four central values of magic square.

2. For the **bordered magic square** of order 25 for the consecutive entries 1 to 625, has the following symmetric results:

- i. $S_{k \times k} := k \times T_{1 \times 1}$;
- ii. $T_{k \times k} := k^2 \times T_{1 \times 1}$;
- iii. $C_{k \times k} := \frac{k-1}{2} \times 8 \times T_{1 \times 1}$.
- iv. $d_{border} := 8 \times T_{1 \times 1}$.

where $k = 3, 5, 7, \dots, 21, 23$ and 25 orders of magic squares appearing **bordered magic square** of order 25, and $T_{1 \times 1} := 313$ is the central value of the magic square.

1.3 Square of Order Sum

Here we shall write bordered magic squares in such a way that the total sum is the square of order of magic squares. For example, for the bordered magic square of order 9, the total sum is 9^2 , etc. This study include decimal entries as well as negative numbers.

Result 1.3. [15] *The general formula the magic sum of each sub-magic square is as follows:*

$$S_{k \times k} := k \times m,$$

where m is the order of **magic square** and k is the order of each **sub-magic squares**.

For example,

- ▶ order 24, $k = 24$, $S_{24 \times m} := 24 \times m$, $m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22$ and 24;
- ▶ order 25, $k = 25$, $S_{25 \times m} := 25 \times m$, $m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23$ and 25.

More results in this direction can be seen in the [1, 2, 4, 3, 5, 6, 7]. Some results on general sum can be seen in author's work [14]. In [15], author wrote different **bordered magic squares** with magic sum always 2020.

In this work, we shall write **bordered magic squares** in such a way that the final sum is 2020. The work is for the **bordered magic squares** of orders 3 to 25. We observe that the **magic sum** of **sub-magic square** give us a symmetric result. The work include fractional, decimal and whole numbers with positive and negative signs.

2 Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020

Recently, author [14] wrote bordered magic squares for the general sum as a natural number n . Based on this idea, the subsections below give bordered magic squares where magic sum is always 2020. In some cases the entries are with fractional numbers, decimal numbers and with natural numbers. The entries are positive and/or negative values.

2.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 3

The bordered magic square of order 3 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

			2020
674 1/3	669 1/3	676 1/3	2020
675 1/3	673 1/3	671 1/3	2020
670 1/3	677 1/3	672 1/3	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020

2.2 Bordered Magic Square of Order 4

The bordered magic square of order 4 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

				2020
510.5	497.5	500.5	511.5	2020
503.5	508.5	505.5	502.5	2020
507.5	504.5	501.5	506.5	2020
498.5	509.5	512.5	499.5	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

In this case the sum of internal four entries is also the same as of magic square sum, i.e., $S_{4 \times 4} := 2020$.

2.3 Bordered Magic Square of Order 5

The bordered magic square of order 5 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

					2020
395	392	412	410	411	2020
415	405	400	407	393	2020
414	406	404	402	394	2020
399	401	408	403	409	2020
397	416	396	398	413	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 1212 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{5}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{5}{5}$$

2.4 Bordered Magic Square of Order 6

The bordered magic square of order 6 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

						2020
350 1/6	348 1/6	321 1/6	354 1/6	322 1/6	324 1/6	2020
320 1/6	342 1/6	329 1/6	332 1/6	343 1/6	353 1/6	2020
326 1/6	335 1/6	340 1/6	337 1/6	334 1/6	347 1/6	2020
328 1/6	339 1/6	336 1/6	333 1/6	338 1/6	345 1/6	2020
346 1/6	330 1/6	341 1/6	344 1/6	331 1/6	327 1/6	2020
349 1/6	325 1/6	352 1/6	319 1/6	351 1/6	323 1/6	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4040}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{4}{6}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{6}{6}$$

2.5 Bordered Magic Square of Order 7

The bordered magic square of order 7 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

							2020
271 4/7	275 4/7	273 4/7	308 4/7	309 4/7	311 4/7	269 4/7	2020
312 4/7	279 4/7	276 4/7	296 4/7	294 4/7	295 4/7	264 4/7	2020
310 4/7	299 4/7	289 4/7	284 4/7	291 4/7	277 4/7	266 4/7	2020
270 4/7	298 4/7	290 4/7	288 4/7	286 4/7	278 4/7	306 4/7	2020
272 4/7	283 4/7	285 4/7	292 4/7	287 4/7	293 4/7	304 4/7	2020
274 4/7	281 4/7	300 4/7	280 4/7	282 4/7	297 4/7	302 4/7	2020
307 4/7	301 4/7	303 4/7	268 4/7	267 4/7	265 4/7	305 4/7	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{6060}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{7}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{7}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{7}{7}$$

2.6 Bordered Magic Square of Order 8

The bordered magic square of order 8 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

228	222	282	284	271	233	273	227	2020
225	266	264	237	270	238	240	280	2020
226	236	258	245	248	259	269	279	2020
231	242	251	256	253	250	263	274	2020
281	244	255	252	249	254	261	224	2020
276	262	246	257	260	247	243	229	2020
275	265	241	268	235	267	239	230	2020
278	283	223	221	234	272	232	277	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1010 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{7}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1515 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{7}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{7}$$

2.7 Bordered Magic Square of Order 9

The bordered magic square of order 9 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

191 4/9	263 4/9	261 4/9	259 4/9	258 4/9	195 4/9	197 4/9	199 4/9	193 4/9	2020
184 4/9	207 4/9	211 4/9	209 4/9	244 4/9	245 4/9	247 4/9	205 4/9	264 4/9	2020
186 4/9	248 4/9	215 4/9	212 4/9	232 4/9	230 4/9	231 4/9	200 4/9	262 4/9	2020
188 4/9	246 4/9	235 4/9	225 4/9	220 4/9	227 4/9	213 4/9	202 4/9	260 4/9	2020
256 4/9	206 4/9	234 4/9	226 4/9	224 4/9	222 4/9	214 4/9	242 4/9	192 4/9	2020
254 4/9	208 4/9	219 4/9	221 4/9	228 4/9	223 4/9	229 4/9	240 4/9	194 4/9	2020
252 4/9	210 4/9	217 4/9	236 4/9	216 4/9	218 4/9	233 4/9	238 4/9	196 4/9	2020
250 4/9	243 4/9	237 4/9	239 4/9	204 4/9	203 4/9	201 4/9	241 4/9	198 4/9	2020
255 4/9	185 4/9	187 4/9	189 4/9	190 4/9	253 4/9	251 4/9	249 4/9	257 4/9	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{2020}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{9}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{9}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{14140}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{9}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{9}{9}$$

2.8 Bordered Magic Square of Order 10

The bordered magic square of order 10 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

										2020
242.5	237.5	167.5	235.5	169.5	165.5	155.5	249.5	153.5	243.5	2020
164.5	177.5	171.5	231.5	233.5	220.5	182.5	222.5	176.5	239.5	2020
240.5	174.5	215.5	213.5	186.5	219.5	187.5	189.5	229.5	163.5	2020
162.5	175.5	185.5	207.5	194.5	197.5	208.5	218.5	228.5	241.5	2020
247.5	180.5	191.5	200.5	205.5	202.5	199.5	212.5	223.5	156.5	2020
152.5	230.5	193.5	204.5	201.5	198.5	203.5	210.5	173.5	251.5	2020
244.5	225.5	211.5	195.5	206.5	209.5	196.5	192.5	178.5	159.5	2020
158.5	224.5	214.5	190.5	217.5	184.5	216.5	188.5	179.5	245.5	2020
246.5	227.5	232.5	172.5	170.5	183.5	221.5	181.5	226.5	157.5	2020
160.5	166.5	236.5	168.5	234.5	238.5	248.5	154.5	250.5	161.5	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 808 = 2020 \times \frac{4}{10}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1212 = 2020 \times \frac{6}{10}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1616 = 2020 \times \frac{8}{10}$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{10}{10}$$

2.9 Bordered Magic Square of Order 11

The bordered magic square of order 11 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

134 7/11	142 7/11	140 7/11	138 7/11	136 7/11	235 7/11	236 7/11	238 7/11	240 7/11	242 7/11	132 7/11	2020
243 7/11	150 7/11	222 7/11	220 7/11	218 7/11	217 7/11	154 7/11	156 7/11	158 7/11	152 7/11	123 7/11	2020
241 7/11	143 7/11	166 7/11	170 7/11	168 7/11	203 7/11	204 7/11	206 7/11	164 7/11	223 7/11	125 7/11	2020
239 7/11	145 7/11	207 7/11	174 7/11	171 7/11	191 7/11	189 7/11	190 7/11	159 7/11	221 7/11	127 7/11	2020
237 7/11	147 7/11	205 7/11	194 7/11	184 7/11	179 7/11	186 7/11	172 7/11	161 7/11	219 7/11	129 7/11	2020
133 7/11	215 7/11	165 7/11	193 7/11	185 7/11	183 7/11	181 7/11	173 7/11	201 7/11	151 7/11	233 7/11	2020
135 7/11	213 7/11	167 7/11	178 7/11	180 7/11	187 7/11	182 7/11	188 7/11	199 7/11	153 7/11	231 7/11	2020
137 7/11	211 7/11	169 7/11	176 7/11	195 7/11	175 7/11	177 7/11	192 7/11	197 7/11	155 7/11	229 7/11	2020
139 7/11	209 7/11	202 7/11	196 7/11	198 7/11	163 7/11	162 7/11	160 7/11	200 7/11	157 7/11	227 7/11	2020
141 7/11	214 7/11	144 7/11	146 7/11	148 7/11	149 7/11	212 7/11	210 7/11	208 7/11	216 7/11	225 7/11	2020
234 7/11	224 7/11	226 7/11	228 7/11	230 7/11	131 7/11	130 7/11	128 7/11	126 7/11	124 7/11	232 7/11	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{6060}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{11}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{11}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{14140}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{11}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18180}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{11}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{11}{11}$$

2.10 Bordered Magic Square of Order 12

The bordered magic square of order 12 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

229 5/6	238 5/6	98 5/6	236 5/6	100 5/6	96 5/6	117 5/6	219 5/6	115 5/6	221 5/6	113 5/6	228 5/6	2020
111 5/6	208 5/6	203 5/6	133 5/6	201 5/6	135 5/6	131 5/6	121 5/6	215 5/6	119 5/6	209 5/6	224 5/6	2020
110 5/6	130 5/6	143 5/6	137 5/6	197 5/6	199 5/6	186 5/6	148 5/6	188 5/6	142 5/6	205 5/6	225 5/6	2020
226 5/6	206 5/6	140 5/6	181 5/6	179 5/6	152 5/6	185 5/6	153 5/6	155 5/6	195 5/6	129 5/6	109 5/6	2020
227 5/6	128 5/6	141 5/6	151 5/6	173 5/6	160 5/6	163 5/6	174 5/6	184 5/6	194 5/6	207 5/6	108 5/6	2020
234 5/6	213 5/6	146 5/6	157 5/6	166 5/6	171 5/6	168 5/6	165 5/6	178 5/6	189 5/6	122 5/6	101 5/6	2020
223 5/6	118 5/6	196 5/6	159 5/6	170 5/6	167 5/6	164 5/6	169 5/6	176 5/6	139 5/6	217 5/6	112 5/6	2020
105 5/6	210 5/6	191 5/6	177 5/6	161 5/6	172 5/6	175 5/6	162 5/6	158 5/6	144 5/6	125 5/6	230 5/6	2020
104 5/6	124 5/6	190 5/6	180 5/6	156 5/6	183 5/6	150 5/6	182 5/6	154 5/6	145 5/6	211 5/6	231 5/6	2020
232 5/6	212 5/6	193 5/6	198 5/6	138 5/6	136 5/6	149 5/6	187 5/6	147 5/6	192 5/6	123 5/6	103 5/6	2020
102 5/6	126 5/6	132 5/6	202 5/6	134 5/6	200 5/6	204 5/6	214 5/6	120 5/6	216 5/6	127 5/6	233 5/6	2020
107 5/6	97 5/6	237 5/6	99 5/6	235 5/6	239 5/6	218 5/6	116 5/6	220 5/6	114 5/6	222 5/6	106 5/6	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{2020}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{4}{12}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1010 = 2020 \times \frac{6}{12}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{4040}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{8}{12}$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5050}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{10}{12}$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{12}{12}$$

2.11 Bordered Magic Square of Order 13

The bordered magic square of order 13 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

226 5/13	217 5/13	219 5/13	221 5/13	223 5/13	225 5/13	227 5/13	79 5/13	77 5/13	75 5/13	73 5/13	71 5/13	82 5/13	2020
72 5/13	106 5/13	114 5/13	112 5/13	110 5/13	108 5/13	207 5/13	208 5/13	210 5/13	212 5/13	214 5/13	104 5/13	238 5/13	2020
74 5/13	215 5/13	122 5/13	194 5/13	192 5/13	190 5/13	189 5/13	126 5/13	128 5/13	130 5/13	124 5/13	95 5/13	236 5/13	2020
76 5/13	213 5/13	115 5/13	138 5/13	142 5/13	140 5/13	175 5/13	176 5/13	178 5/13	136 5/13	195 5/13	97 5/13	234 5/13	2020
78 5/13	211 5/13	117 5/13	179 5/13	146 5/13	143 5/13	163 5/13	161 5/13	162 5/13	131 5/13	193 5/13	99 5/13	232 5/13	2020
80 5/13	209 5/13	119 5/13	177 5/13	166 5/13	156 5/13	151 5/13	158 5/13	144 5/13	133 5/13	191 5/13	101 5/13	230 5/13	2020
81 5/13	105 5/13	187 5/13	137 5/13	165 5/13	157 5/13	155 5/13	153 5/13	145 5/13	173 5/13	123 5/13	205 5/13	229 5/13	2020
224 5/13	107 5/13	185 5/13	139 5/13	150 5/13	152 5/13	159 5/13	154 5/13	160 5/13	171 5/13	125 5/13	203 5/13	86 5/13	2020
222 5/13	109 5/13	183 5/13	141 5/13	148 5/13	167 5/13	147 5/13	149 5/13	164 5/13	169 5/13	127 5/13	201 5/13	88 5/13	2020
220 5/13	111 5/13	181 5/13	174 5/13	168 5/13	170 5/13	135 5/13	134 5/13	132 5/13	172 5/13	129 5/13	199 5/13	90 5/13	2020
218 5/13	113 5/13	186 5/13	116 5/13	118 5/13	120 5/13	121 5/13	184 5/13	182 5/13	180 5/13	188 5/13	197 5/13	92 5/13	2020
216 5/13	206 5/13	196 5/13	198 5/13	200 5/13	202 5/13	103 5/13	102 5/13	100 5/13	98 5/13	96 5/13	204 5/13	94 5/13	2020
228 5/13	93 5/13	91 5/13	89 5/13	87 5/13	85 5/13	83 5/13	231 5/13	233 5/13	235 5/13	237 5/13	239 5/13	84 5/13	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{6060}{13} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{13}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{13} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{13}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{14140}{13} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{13}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18180}{13} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{13}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{22220}{13} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{13}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{13}{13}$$

2.12 Bordered Magic Square of Order 14

The bordered magic square of order 14 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

59 11/14	53 11/14	233 11/14	55 11/14	231 11/14	57 11/14	241 11/14	52 11/14	227 11/14	61 11/14	225 11/14	63 11/14	223 11/14	229 11/14	2020
240 11/14	205 11/14	214 11/14	74 11/14	212 11/14	76 11/14	72 11/14	93 11/14	195 11/14	91 11/14	197 11/14	89 11/14	204 11/14	47 11/14	2020
48 11/14	87 11/14	184 11/14	179 11/14	109 11/14	177 11/14	111 11/14	107 11/14	97 11/14	191 11/14	95 11/14	185 11/14	200 11/14	239 11/14	2020
238 11/14	86 11/14	106 11/14	119 11/14	113 11/14	173 11/14	175 11/14	162 11/14	124 11/14	164 11/14	118 11/14	181 11/14	201 11/14	49 11/14	2020
50 11/14	202 11/14	182 11/14	116 11/14	157 11/14	155 11/14	128 11/14	161 11/14	129 11/14	131 11/14	171 11/14	105 11/14	85 11/14	237 11/14	2020
236 11/14	203 11/14	104 11/14	117 11/14	127 11/14	149 11/14	136 11/14	139 11/14	150 11/14	160 11/14	170 11/14	183 11/14	84 11/14	51 11/14	2020
222 11/14	210 11/14	189 11/14	122 11/14	133 11/14	142 11/14	147 11/14	144 11/14	141 11/14	154 11/14	165 11/14	98 11/14	77 11/14	65 11/14	2020
216 11/14	199 11/14	94 11/14	172 11/14	135 11/14	146 11/14	143 11/14	140 11/14	145 11/14	152 11/14	115 11/14	193 11/14	88 11/14	71 11/14	2020
70 11/14	81 11/14	186 11/14	167 11/14	153 11/14	137 11/14	148 11/14	151 11/14	138 11/14	134 11/14	120 11/14	101 11/14	206 11/14	217 11/14	2020
218 11/14	80 11/14	100 11/14	166 11/14	156 11/14	132 11/14	159 11/14	126 11/14	158 11/14	130 11/14	121 11/14	187 11/14	207 11/14	69 11/14	2020
68 11/14	208 11/14	188 11/14	169 11/14	174 11/14	114 11/14	112 11/14	125 11/14	163 11/14	123 11/14	168 11/14	99 11/14	79 11/14	219 11/14	2020
220 11/14	78 11/14	102 11/14	108 11/14	178 11/14	110 11/14	176 11/14	180 11/14	190 11/14	96 11/14	192 11/14	103 11/14	209 11/14	67 11/14	2020
66 11/14	83 11/14	73 11/14	213 11/14	75 11/14	211 11/14	215 11/14	194 11/14	92 11/14	196 11/14	90 11/14	198 11/14	82 11/14	221 11/14	2020
58 11/14	234 11/14	54 11/14	232 11/14	56 11/14	230 11/14	46 11/14	235 11/14	60 11/14	226 11/14	62 11/14	224 11/14	64 11/14	228 11/14	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4040}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{4}{14} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6060}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{6}{14} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8080}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{8}{14} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10100}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{10}{14} \\
 S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12120}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{12}{14} \\
 S_{14 \times 14} &:= 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{14}{14}.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.13 Bordered Magic Square of Order 15

The bordered magic square of order 15 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

231 2/3	220 2/3	222 2/3	224 2/3	226 2/3	228 2/3	230 2/3	232 2/3	32 2/3	30 2/3	28 2/3	26 2/3	24 2/3	22 2/3	35 2/3	2020
23 2/3	205 2/3	196 2/3	198 2/3	200 2/3	202 2/3	204 2/3	206 2/3	58 2/3	56 2/3	54 2/3	52 2/3	50 2/3	61 2/3	245 2/3	2020
25 2/3	51 2/3	85 2/3	93 2/3	91 2/3	89 2/3	87 2/3	186 2/3	187 2/3	189 2/3	191 2/3	193 2/3	83 2/3	217 2/3	243 2/3	2020
27 2/3	53 2/3	194 2/3	101 2/3	173 2/3	171 2/3	169 2/3	168 2/3	105 2/3	107 2/3	109 2/3	103 2/3	74 2/3	215 2/3	241 2/3	2020
29 2/3	55 2/3	192 2/3	94 2/3	117 2/3	121 2/3	119 2/3	154 2/3	155 2/3	157 2/3	115 2/3	174 2/3	76 2/3	213 2/3	239 2/3	2020
31 2/3	57 2/3	190 2/3	96 2/3	158 2/3	125 2/3	122 2/3	142 2/3	140 2/3	141 2/3	110 2/3	172 2/3	78 2/3	211 2/3	237 2/3	2020
33 2/3	59 2/3	188 2/3	98 2/3	156 2/3	145 2/3	135 2/3	130 2/3	137 2/3	123 2/3	112 2/3	170 2/3	80 2/3	209 2/3	235 2/3	2020
34 2/3	60 2/3	84 2/3	166 2/3	116 2/3	144 2/3	136 2/3	134 2/3	132 2/3	124 2/3	152 2/3	102 2/3	184 2/3	208 2/3	234 2/3	2020
229 2/3	203 2/3	86 2/3	164 2/3	118 2/3	129 2/3	131 2/3	138 2/3	133 2/3	139 2/3	150 2/3	104 2/3	182 2/3	65 2/3	39 2/3	2020
227 2/3	201 2/3	88 2/3	162 2/3	120 2/3	127 2/3	146 2/3	126 2/3	128 2/3	143 2/3	148 2/3	106 2/3	180 2/3	67 2/3	41 2/3	2020
225 2/3	199 2/3	90 2/3	160 2/3	153 2/3	147 2/3	149 2/3	114 2/3	113 2/3	111 2/3	151 2/3	108 2/3	178 2/3	69 2/3	43 2/3	2020
223 2/3	197 2/3	92 2/3	165 2/3	95 2/3	97 2/3	99 2/3	100 2/3	163 2/3	161 2/3	159 2/3	167 2/3	176 2/3	71 2/3	45 2/3	2020
221 2/3	195 2/3	185 2/3	175 2/3	177 2/3	179 2/3	181 2/3	82 2/3	81 2/3	79 2/3	77 2/3	75 2/3	183 2/3	73 2/3	47 2/3	2020
219 2/3	207 2/3	72 2/3	70 2/3	68 2/3	66 2/3	64 2/3	62 2/3	210 2/3	212 2/3	214 2/3	216 2/3	218 2/3	63 2/3	49 2/3	2020
233 2/3	48 2/3	46 2/3	44 2/3	42 2/3	40 2/3	38 2/3	36 2/3	236 2/3	238 2/3	240 2/3	242 2/3	244 2/3	246 2/3	37 2/3	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 404 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{15}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{2020}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{15}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{2828}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{15}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1212 = 2020 \times \frac{9}{15}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{4444}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{15}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{5252}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{13}{15}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{15}{15}$$

2.14 Bordered Magic Square of Order 16

The bordered magic square of order 16 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

239.75	19.75	233.75	17.75	16.75	236.75	237.75	246.75	231.75	11.75	10.75	242.75	8.75	244.75	6.75	13.75	2020
252.75	41.75	35.75	215.75	37.75	213.75	39.75	223.75	34.75	209.75	43.75	207.75	45.75	205.75	211.75	-0.25	2020
0.75	222.75	187.75	196.75	56.75	194.75	58.75	54.75	75.75	177.75	73.75	179.75	71.75	186.75	29.75	251.75	2020
250.75	30.75	69.75	166.75	161.75	91.75	159.75	93.75	89.75	79.75	173.75	77.75	167.75	182.75	221.75	1.75	2020
2.75	220.75	68.75	88.75	101.75	95.75	155.75	157.75	144.75	106.75	146.75	100.75	163.75	183.75	31.75	249.75	2020
248.75	32.75	184.75	164.75	98.75	139.75	137.75	110.75	143.75	111.75	113.75	153.75	87.75	67.75	219.75	3.75	2020
4.75	218.75	185.75	86.75	99.75	109.75	131.75	118.75	121.75	132.75	142.75	152.75	165.75	66.75	33.75	247.75	2020
-1.25	204.75	192.75	171.75	104.75	115.75	124.75	129.75	126.75	123.75	136.75	147.75	80.75	59.75	47.75	253.75	2020
27.75	198.75	181.75	76.75	154.75	117.75	128.75	125.75	122.75	127.75	134.75	97.75	175.75	70.75	53.75	224.75	2020
225.75	52.75	63.75	168.75	149.75	135.75	119.75	130.75	133.75	120.75	116.75	102.75	83.75	188.75	199.75	26.75	2020
25.75	200.75	62.75	82.75	148.75	138.75	114.75	141.75	108.75	140.75	112.75	103.75	169.75	189.75	51.75	226.75	2020
227.75	50.75	190.75	170.75	151.75	156.75	96.75	94.75	107.75	145.75	105.75	150.75	81.75	61.75	201.75	24.75	2020
23.75	202.75	60.75	84.75	90.75	160.75	92.75	158.75	162.75	172.75	78.75	174.75	85.75	191.75	49.75	228.75	2020
229.75	48.75	65.75	55.75	195.75	57.75	193.75	197.75	176.75	74.75	178.75	72.75	180.75	64.75	203.75	22.75	2020
21.75	40.75	216.75	36.75	214.75	38.75	212.75	28.75	217.75	42.75	208.75	44.75	206.75	46.75	210.75	230.75	2020
238.75	232.75	18.75	234.75	235.75	15.75	14.75	5.75	20.75	240.75	241.75	9.75	243.75	7.75	245.75	12.75	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 64 = 505 = 2020 \times \frac{4}{16} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 192 = 1515 = 2020 \times \frac{12}{16} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 96 = 757.5 = 2020 \times \frac{6}{16} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 224 = 1767.5 = 2020 \times \frac{14}{16} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 128 = 1010 = 2020 \times \frac{8}{16} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 246 = 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{16}{16} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 160 = 1265.5 = 2020 \times \frac{10}{16} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

2.15 Bordered Magic Square of Order 17

The bordered magic square of order 17 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

-10 3/17	261 14/17	259 14/17	257 14/17	255 14/17	253 14/17	251 14/17	249 14/17	248 14/17	-6 3/17	-4 3/17	-2 3/17	- 3/17	1 14/17	3 14/17	5 14/17	-8 3/17	2020
-25 3/17	215 14/17	204 14/17	206 14/17	208 14/17	210 14/17	212 14/17	214 14/17	216 14/17	16 14/17	14 14/17	12 14/17	10 14/17	8 14/17	6 14/17	19 14/17	262 14/17	2020
-23 3/17	7 14/17	189 14/17	180 14/17	182 14/17	184 14/17	186 14/17	188 14/17	190 14/17	42 14/17	40 14/17	38 14/17	36 14/17	34 14/17	45 14/17	229 14/17	260 14/17	2020
-21 3/17	9 14/17	35 14/17	69 14/17	77 14/17	75 14/17	73 14/17	71 14/17	170 14/17	171 14/17	173 14/17	175 14/17	177 14/17	67 14/17	201 14/17	227 14/17	258 14/17	2020
-19 3/17	11 14/17	37 14/17	178 14/17	85 14/17	157 14/17	155 14/17	153 14/17	152 14/17	89 14/17	91 14/17	93 14/17	87 14/17	58 14/17	199 14/17	225 14/17	256 14/17	2020
-17 3/17	13 14/17	39 14/17	176 14/17	78 14/17	101 14/17	105 14/17	103 14/17	138 14/17	139 14/17	141 14/17	99 14/17	158 14/17	60 14/17	197 14/17	223 14/17	254 14/17	2020
-15 3/17	15 14/17	41 14/17	174 14/17	80 14/17	142 14/17	109 14/17	106 14/17	126 14/17	124 14/17	125 14/17	94 14/17	156 14/17	62 14/17	195 14/17	221 14/17	252 14/17	2020
-13 3/17	17 14/17	43 14/17	172 14/17	82 14/17	140 14/17	129 14/17	119 14/17	114 14/17	121 14/17	107 14/17	96 14/17	154 14/17	64 14/17	193 14/17	219 14/17	250 14/17	2020
246 14/17	18 14/17	44 14/17	68 14/17	150 14/17	100 14/17	128 14/17	120 14/17	118 14/17	116 14/17	108 14/17	136 14/17	86 14/17	168 14/17	192 14/17	218 14/17	-9 3/17	2020
244 14/17	213 14/17	187 14/17	70 14/17	148 14/17	102 14/17	113 14/17	115 14/17	122 14/17	117 14/17	123 14/17	134 14/17	88 14/17	166 14/17	49 14/17	23 14/17	-7 3/17	2020
242 14/17	211 14/17	185 14/17	72 14/17	146 14/17	104 14/17	111 14/17	130 14/17	110 14/17	112 14/17	127 14/17	132 14/17	90 14/17	164 14/17	51 14/17	25 14/17	-5 3/17	2020
240 14/17	209 14/17	183 14/17	74 14/17	144 14/17	137 14/17	131 14/17	133 14/17	98 14/17	97 14/17	95 14/17	135 14/17	92 14/17	162 14/17	53 14/17	27 14/17	-3 3/17	2020
238 14/17	207 14/17	181 14/17	76 14/17	149 14/17	79 14/17	81 14/17	83 14/17	84 14/17	147 14/17	145 14/17	143 14/17	151 14/17	160 14/17	55 14/17	29 14/17	-1 3/17	2020
236 14/17	205 14/17	179 14/17	169 14/17	159 14/17	161 14/17	163 14/17	165 14/17	66 14/17	65 14/17	63 14/17	61 14/17	59 14/17	167 14/17	57 14/17	31 14/17	14/17	2020
234 14/17	203 14/17	191 14/17	56 14/17	54 14/17	52 14/17	50 14/17	48 14/17	46 14/17	194 14/17	196 14/17	198 14/17	200 14/17	202 14/17	47 14/17	33 14/17	2 14/17	2020
232 14/17	217 14/17	32 14/17	30 14/17	28 14/17	26 14/17	24 14/17	22 14/17	20 14/17	220 14/17	222 14/17	224 14/17	226 14/17	228 14/17	230 14/17	21 14/17	4 14/17	2020
245 14/17	-24 3/17	-22 3/17	-20 3/17	-18 3/17	-16 3/17	-14 3/17	-12 3/17	-11 3/17	243 14/17	241 14/17	239 14/17	237 14/17	235 14/17	233 14/17	231 14/17	247 14/17	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{6060}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{17}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{17}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{14140}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{17}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18180}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{17}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{22220}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{17}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{26260}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{13}{17}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30300}{17} = 2020 \times \frac{15}{17}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{17}{17}$$

2.16 Bordered Magic Square of Order 18

The bordered magic square of order 18 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

256 13/18	-25 5/18	250 13/18	-27 5/18	252 13/18	-29 5/18	254 13/18	-31 5/18	265 13/18	-49 5/18	258 13/18	-35 5/18	260 13/18	-37 5/18	262 13/18	-39 5/18	264 13/18	-33 5/18	2020
247 13/18	225 13/18	5 13/18	219 13/18	3 13/18	2 13/18	222 13/18	223 13/18	232 13/18	217 13/18	-2 5/18	-3 5/18	228 13/18	-5 5/18	230 13/18	-7 5/18	- 5/18	-23 5/18	2020
-22 5/18	238 13/18	27 13/18	21 13/18	20113/18	23 13/18	199 13/18	25 13/18	209 13/18	20 13/18	195 13/18	29 13/18	193 13/18	31 13/18	191 13/18	197 13/18	-14 5/18	244 13/18	2020
245 13/18	-13 5/18	208 13/18	173 13/18	182 13/18	42 13/18	180 13/18	44 13/18	40 13/18	61 13/18	163 13/18	59 13/18	165 13/18	57 13/18	172 13/18	15 13/18	237 13/18	-21 5/18	2020
-20 5/18	236 13/18	16 13/18	55 13/18	152 13/18	147 13/18	77 13/18	145 13/18	79 13/18	75 13/18	65 13/18	159 13/18	63 13/18	153 13/18	168 13/18	207 13/18	-12 5/18	244 13/18	2020
243 13/18	-11 5/18	206 13/18	54 13/18	74 13/18	87 13/18	81 13/18	141 13/18	143 13/18	130 13/18	92 13/18	132 13/18	86 13/18	149 13/18	169 13/18	17 13/18	235 13/18	-19 5/18	2020
-18 5/18	234 13/18	18 13/18	170 13/18	150 13/18	84 13/18	125 13/18	123 13/18	96 13/18	129 13/18	97 13/18	99 13/18	139 13/18	73 13/18	53 13/18	205 13/18	-10 5/18	242 13/18	2020
241 13/18	-9 5/18	204 13/18	171 13/18	72 13/18	85 13/18	95 13/18	117 13/18	104 13/18	107 13/18	118 13/18	128 13/18	138 13/18	151 13/18	52 13/18	19 13/18	233 13/18	-17 5/18	2020
-16 5/18	-15 5/18	190 13/18	178 13/18	157 13/18	90 13/18	101 13/18	110 13/18	115 13/18	112 13/18	109 13/18	122 13/18	133 13/18	66 13/18	45 13/18	33 13/18	239 13/18	240 13/18	2020
-24 5/18	13 13/18	184 13/18	167 13/18	62 13/18	140 13/18	103 13/18	114 13/18	111 13/18	108 13/18	113 13/18	120 13/18	83 13/18	161 13/18	56 13/18	39 13/18	210 13/18	248 13/18	2020
-42 5/18	211 13/18	38 13/18	49 13/18	154 13/18	135 13/18	121 13/18	105 13/18	116 13/18	119 13/18	106 13/18	102 13/18	88 13/18	69 13/18	174 13/18	185 13/18	12 13/18	266 13/18	2020
267 13/18	11 13/18	186 13/18	48 13/18	68 13/18	134 13/18	124 13/18	100 13/18	127 13/18	94 13/18	126 13/18	98 13/18	89 13/18	155 13/18	175 13/18	37 13/18	212 13/18	-43 5/18	2020
-44 5/18	213 13/18	36 13/18	176 13/18	156 13/18	137 13/18	142 13/18	82 13/18	80 13/18	93 13/18	131 13/18	91 13/18	136 13/18	67 13/18	47 13/18	187 13/18	10 13/18	268 13/18	2020
269 13/18	9 13/18	188 13/18	46 13/18	70 13/18	76 13/18	146 13/18	78 13/18	144 13/18	148 13/18	158 13/18	64 13/18	160 13/18	71 13/18	177 13/18	35 13/18	214 13/18	-45 5/18	2020
-46 5/18	215 13/18	34 13/18	51 13/18	41 13/18	181 13/18	43 13/18	179 13/18	183 13/18	162 13/18	60 13/18	164 13/18	58 13/18	166 13/18	50 13/18	189 13/18	8 13/18	270 13/18	2020
271 13/18	7 13/18	26 13/18	202 13/18	22 13/18	200 13/18	24 13/18	198 13/18	14 13/18	203 13/18	28 13/18	194 13/18	30 13/18	192 13/18	32 13/18	196 13/18	216 13/18	-47 5/18	2020
-48 5/18	224 13/18	218 13/18	4 13/18	220 13/18	221 13/18	1 13/18	13/18	-8 5/18	6 13/18	226 13/18	227 13/18	-4 5/18	229 13/18	-6 5/18	231 13/18	-1 5/18	272 13/18	2020
257 13/18	249 13/18	-26 5/18	251 13/18	-28 5/18	253 13/18	-30 5/18	255 13/18	-41 5/18	273 13/18	-34 5/18	259 13/18	-36 5/18	261 13/18	-38 5/18	263 13/18	-40 5/18	-32 5/18	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4040}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{4}{18} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{4040}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{12}{18} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{2020}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{6}{18} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{1414}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{14}{18} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8080}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{8}{18} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16160}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{16}{18} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10100}{9} = 2020 \times \frac{10}{18} & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{18}{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.17 Bordered Magic Square of Order 19

The bordered magic square of order 19 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

-54 13/19	-38 13/19	-40 13/19	-42 13/19	-44 13/19	-46 13/19	-48 13/19	-50 13/19	-52 13/19	270 6/19	271 6/19	273 6/19	275 6/19	277 6/19	279 6/19	281 6/19	283 6/19	285 6/19	-56 13/19	2020
286 6/19	-22 13/19	249 6/19	247 6/19	245 6/19	243 6/19	241 6/19	239 6/19	237 6/19	236 6/19	-18 13/19	-16 13/19	-14 13/19	-12 13/19	-10 13/19	-8 13/19	-6 13/19	-20 13/19	-73 13/19	2020
284 6/19	-37 13/19	203 6/19	192 6/19	194 6/19	196 6/19	198 6/19	200 6/19	202 6/19	204 6/19	4 6/19	2 6/19	6/19	-1 13/19	-3 13/19	-5 13/19	7 6/19	250 6/19	-71 13/19	2020
282 6/19	-35 13/19	-4 13/19	177 6/19	168 6/19	170 6/19	172 6/19	174 6/19	176 6/19	178 6/19	30 6/19	28 6/19	26 6/19	24 6/19	22 6/19	33 6/19	217 6/19	248 6/19	-69 13/19	2020
280 6/19	-33 13/19	-2 13/19	23 6/19	57 6/19	65 6/19	63 6/19	61 6/19	59 6/19	158 6/19	159 6/19	161 6/19	163 6/19	165 6/19	55 6/19	189 6/19	215 6/19	246 6/19	-67 13/19	2020
278 6/19	-31 13/19	-13/19	25 6/19	166 6/19	73 6/19	145 6/19	143 6/19	141 6/19	140 6/19	77 6/19	79 6/19	81 6/19	75 6/19	46 6/19	187 6/19	213 6/19	244 6/19	-65 13/19	2020
276 6/19	-29 13/19	1 6/19	27 6/19	164 6/19	66 6/19	89 6/19	93 6/19	91 6/19	126 6/19	127 6/19	129 6/19	87 6/19	146 6/19	48 6/19	185 6/19	211 6/19	242 6/19	-63 13/19	2020
274 6/19	-27 13/19	3 6/19	29 6/19	162 6/19	68 6/19	130 6/19	97 6/19	94 6/19	114 6/19	112 6/19	113 6/19	82 6/19	144 6/19	50 6/19	183 6/19	209 6/19	240 6/19	-61 13/19	2020
272 6/19	-25 13/19	5 6/19	31 6/19	160 6/19	70 6/19	128 6/19	117 6/19	107 6/19	102 6/19	109 6/19	95 6/19	84 6/19	142 6/19	52 6/19	181 6/19	207 6/19	238 6/19	-59 13/19	2020
-55 13/19	234 6/19	6 6/19	32 6/19	56 6/19	138 6/19	88 6/19	116 6/19	108 6/19	106 6/19	104 6/19	96 6/19	124 6/19	74 6/19	156 6/19	180 6/19	206 6/19	-21 13/19	268 6/19	2020
-53 13/19	232 6/19	201 6/19	175 6/19	58 6/19	136 6/19	90 6/19	101 6/19	103 6/19	110 6/19	105 6/19	111 6/19	122 6/19	76 6/19	154 6/19	37 6/19	11 6/19	-19 13/19	266 6/19	2020
-51 13/19	230 6/19	199 6/19	173 6/19	60 6/19	134 6/19	92 6/19	99 6/19	118 6/19	98 6/19	100 6/19	115 6/19	120 6/19	78 6/19	152 6/19	39 6/19	13 6/19	-17 13/19	264 6/19	2020
-49 13/19	228 6/19	197 6/19	171 6/19	62 6/19	132 6/19	125 6/19	119 6/19	121 6/19	86 6/19	85 6/19	83 6/19	123 6/19	80 6/19	150 6/19	41 6/19	15 6/19	-15 13/19	262 6/19	2020
-47 13/19	226 6/19	195 6/19	169 6/19	64 6/19	137 6/19	67 6/19	69 6/19	71 6/19	72 6/19	135 6/19	133 6/19	131 6/19	139 6/19	148 6/19	43 6/19	17 6/19	-13 13/19	260 6/19	2020
-45 13/19	224 6/19	193 6/19	167 6/19	157 6/19	147 6/19	149 6/19	151 6/19	153 6/19	54 6/19	53 6/19	51 6/19	49 6/19	47 6/19	155 6/19	45 6/19	19 6/19	-11 13/19	258 6/19	2020
-43 13/19	222 6/19	191 6/19	179 6/19	44 6/19	42 6/19	40 6/19	38 6/19	36 6/19	34 6/19	182 6/19	184 6/19	186 6/19	188 6/19	190 6/19	35 6/19	21 6/19	-9 13/19	256 6/19	2020
-41 13/19	220 6/19	205 6/19	20 6/19	18 6/19	16 6/19	14 6/19	12 6/19	10 6/19	8 6/19	208 6/19	210 6/19	212 6/19	214 6/19	216 6/19	218 6/19	9 6/19	-7 13/19	254 6/19	2020
-39 13/19	233 6/19	-36 13/19	-34 13/19	-32 13/19	-30 13/19	-28 13/19	-26 13/19	-24 13/19	-23 13/19	231 6/19	229 6/19	227 6/19	225 6/19	223 6/19	221 6/19	219 6/19	235 6/19	252 6/19	2020
269 6/19	251 6/19	253 6/19	255 6/19	257 6/19	259 6/19	261 6/19	263 6/19	265 6/19	-57 13/19	-58 13/19	-60 13/19	-62 13/19	-64 13/19	-66 13/19	-68 13/19	-70 13/19	-72 13/19	267 6/19	2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{6060}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{19}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{19}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{14140}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{19}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18180}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{19}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{22220}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{19}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{26260}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{13}{19}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30300}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{15}{19}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{34340}{19} = 2020 \times \frac{17}{19}$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{19}{19}$$

2.18 Bordered Magic Square of Order 20

The bordered magic square of order 20 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

-80.5	271.5	-68.5	269.5	-66.5	267.5	-64.5	265.5	-62.5	263.5	300.5	292.5	-91.5	294.5	-93.5	296.5	-95.5	298.5	-97.5	-79.5	2020
290.5	245.5	-36.5	239.5	-38.5	241.5	-40.5	243.5	-42.5	254.5	-60.5	247.5	-46.5	249.5	-48.5	251.5	-50.5	253.5	-44.5	-88.5	2020
-87.5	236.5	214.5	-5.5	208.5	-7.5	-8.5	211.5	212.5	221.5	206.5	-13.5	-14.5	217.5	-16.5	219.5	-18.5	-11.5	-34.5	289.5	2020
288.5	-33.5	227.5	16.5	10.5	190.5	12.5	188.5	14.5	198.5	9.5	184.5	18.5	182.5	20.5	180.5	186.5	-25.5	235.5	-86.5	2020
-85.5	234.5	-24.5	197.5	162.5	171.5	31.5	169.5	33.5	29.5	50.5	152.5	48.5	154.5	46.5	161.5	4.5	226.5	-32.5	287.5	2020
286.5	-31.5	225.5	5.5	44.5	141.5	136.5	66.5	134.5	68.5	64.5	54.5	148.5	52.5	142.5	157.5	196.5	-23.5	233.5	-84.5	2020
-83.5	232.5	-22.5	195.5	43.5	63.5	76.5	70.5	130.5	132.5	119.5	81.5	121.5	75.5	138.5	158.5	6.5	224.5	-30.5	285.5	2020
284.5	-29.5	223.5	7.5	159.5	139.5	73.5	114.5	112.5	85.5	118.5	86.5	88.5	128.5	62.5	42.5	194.5	-21.5	231.5	-82.5	2020
283.5	230.5	-20.5	193.5	160.5	61.5	74.5	84.5	106.5	93.5	96.5	107.5	117.5	127.5	140.5	41.5	8.5	222.5	-28.5	-81.5	2020
-70.5	-27.5	-26.5	179.5	167.5	146.5	79.5	90.5	99.5	104.5	101.5	98.5	111.5	122.5	55.5	34.5	22.5	228.5	229.5	272.5	2020
-89.5	-35.5	2.5	173.5	156.5	51.5	129.5	92.5	103.5	100.5	97.5	102.5	109.5	72.5	150.5	45.5	28.5	199.5	237.5	291.5	2020
-78.5	-53.5	200.5	27.5	38.5	143.5	124.5	110.5	94.5	105.5	108.5	95.5	91.5	77.5	58.5	163.5	174.5	1.5	255.5	280.5	2020
-77.5	256.5	0.5	175.5	37.5	57.5	123.5	113.5	89.5	116.5	83.5	115.5	87.5	78.5	144.5	164.5	26.5	201.5	-54.5	279.5	2020
278.5	-55.5	202.5	25.5	165.5	145.5	126.5	131.5	71.5	69.5	82.5	120.5	80.5	125.5	56.5	36.5	176.5	-0.5	257.5	-76.5	2020
277.5	258.5	-1.5	177.5	35.5	59.5	65.5	135.5	67.5	133.5	137.5	147.5	53.5	149.5	60.5	166.5	24.5	203.5	-56.5	-75.5	2020
-74.5	-57.5	204.5	23.5	40.5	30.5	170.5	32.5	168.5	172.5	151.5	49.5	153.5	47.5	155.5	39.5	178.5	-2.5	259.5	276.5	2020
275.5	260.5	-3.5	15.5	191.5	11.5	189.5	13.5	187.5	3.5	192.5	17.5	183.5	19.5	181.5	21.5	185.5	205.5	-58.5	-73.5	2020
-72.5	-59.5	213.5	207.5	-6.5	209.5	210.5	-9.5	-10.5	-19.5	-4.5	215.5	216.5	-15.5	218.5	-17.5	220.5	-12.5	261.5	274.5	2020
273.5	246.5	238.5	-37.5	240.5	-39.5	242.5	-41.5	244.5	-52.5	262.5	-45.5	248.5	-47.5	250.5	-49.5	252.5	-51.5	-43.5	-71.5	2020
281.5	-69.5	270.5	-67.5	268.5	-65.5	266.5	-63.5	264.5	-61.5	-98.5	-90.5	293.5	-92.5	295.5	-94.5	297.5	-96.5	299.5	282.5	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 404 = 2020 \times \frac{4}{20} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 1414 = 2020 \times \frac{14}{20} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 606 = 2020 \times \frac{6}{20} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 1616 = 2020 \times \frac{16}{20} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 808 = 2020 \times \frac{8}{20} & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 1818 = 2020 \times \frac{18}{20} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 1010 = 2020 \times \frac{10}{20} & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{20}{20} \\
 S_{12 \times 12} &:= 1212 = 2020 \times \frac{12}{20} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

2.19 Bordered Magic Square of Order 21

The bordered magic square of order 21 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

295 4/21	278 4/21	280 4/21	282 4/21	284 4/21	286 4/21	288 4/21	290 4/21	292 4/21	294 4/21	296 4/21	-107 17/21	-109 17/21	-111 17/21	-113 17/21	-115 17/21	-117 17/21	-119 17/21	-121 17/21	-123 17/21	-104 17/21	2020	
-122 17/21	259 4/21	-49 17/21	-51 17/21	-53 17/21	-55 17/21	-57 17/21	-59 17/21	-61 17/21	-63 17/21	-65 17/21	262 4/21	264 4/21	266 4/21	268 4/21	270 4/21	272 4/21	274 4/21	276 4/21	-64 17/21	315 4/21	2020	
-120 17/21	241 4/21	225 4/21	-17 17/21	-19 17/21	-21 17/21	-23 17/21	-25 17/21	-27 17/21	-29 17/21	-31 17/21	228 4/21	230 4/21	232 4/21	234 4/21	236 4/21	238 4/21	240 4/21	-30 17/21	-48 17/21	313 4/21	2020	
-118 17/21	243 4/21	209 4/21	195 4/21	181 4/21	183 4/21	185 4/21	187 4/21	189 4/21	191 4/21	-3 17/21	-4 17/21	-6 17/21	-8 17/21	-10 17/21	-12 17/21	-14 17/21	193 4/21	-16 17/21	-50 17/21	311 4/21	2020	
-116 17/21	245 4/21	211 4/21	10 4/21	23 4/21	12 4/21	14 4/21	16 4/21	18 4/21	20 4/21	168 4/21	166 4/21	164 4/21	162 4/21	160 4/21	158 4/21	167 4/21	182 4/21	-18 17/21	-52 17/21	309 4/21	2020	
-114 17/21	247 4/21	213 4/21	8 4/21	179 4/21	45 4/21	36 4/21	38 4/21	40 4/21	42 4/21	146 4/21	144 4/21	142 4/21	140 4/21	138 4/21	145 4/21	13 4/21	184 4/21	-20 17/21	-54 17/21	307 4/21	2020	
-112 17/21	249 4/21	215 4/21	6 4/21	177 4/21	155 4/21	127 4/21	57 4/21	59 4/21	61 4/21	62 4/21	125 4/21	123 4/21	121 4/21	129 4/21	37 4/21	15 4/21	186 4/21	-22 17/21	-56 17/21	305 4/21	2020	
-110 17/21	251 4/21	217 4/21	4 4/21	175 4/21	153 4/21	122 4/21	113 4/21	73 4/21	75 4/21	76 4/21	111 4/21	109 4/21	115 4/21	70 4/21	39 4/21	17 4/21	188 4/21	-24 17/21	-58 17/21	303 4/21	2020	
-108 17/21	253 4/21	219 4/21	2 4/21	173 4/21	151 4/21	124 4/21	110 4/21	105 4/21	101 4/21	86 4/21	85 4/21	103 4/21	82 4/21	68 4/21	41 4/21	19 4/21	190 4/21	-26 17/21	-60 17/21	301 4/21	2020	
-106 17/21	255 4/21	221 4/21	4/21	171 4/21	149 4/21	126 4/21	112 4/21	90 4/21	93 4/21	98 4/21	97 4/21	102 4/21	80 4/21	66 4/21	43 4/21	21 4/21	192 4/21	-28 17/21	-62 17/21	299 4/21	2020	
-105 17/21	-67 17/21	-33 17/21	-1 17/21	170 4/21	148 4/21	128 4/21	114 4/21	88 4/21	100 4/21	96 4/21	92 4/21	104 4/21	78 4/21	64 4/21	44 4/21	22 4/21	194 4/21	226 4/21	260 4/21	298 4/21	2020	
293 4/21	-68 17/21	-34 17/21	198 4/21	27 4/21	49 4/21	60 4/21	74 4/21	108 4/21	95 4/21	94 4/21	99 4/21	84 4/21	118 4/21	132 4/21	143 4/21	165 4/21	-5 17/21	227 4/21	261 4/21	-100 17/21	2020	
291 4/21	-70 17/21	-36 17/21	200 4/21	29 4/21	51 4/21	58 4/21	72 4/21	89 4/21	91 4/21	106 4/21	107 4/21	87 4/21	120 4/21	134 4/21	141 4/21	163 4/21	-7 17/21	229 4/21	263 4/21	-98 17/21	2020	
289 4/21	-72 17/21	-38 17/21	202 4/21	31 4/21	53 4/21	56 4/21	77 4/21	119 4/21	117 4/21	116 4/21	81 4/21	83 4/21	79 4/21	136 4/21	139 4/21	161 4/21	-9 17/21	231 4/21	265 4/21	-96 17/21	2020	
287 4/21	-74 17/21	-40 17/21	204 4/21	33 4/21	55 4/21	63 4/21	135 4/21	133 4/21	131 4/21	130 4/21	67 4/21	69 4/21	71 4/21	65 4/21	137 4/21	159 4/21	-11 17/21	233 4/21	267 4/21	-94 17/21	2020	
285 4/21	-76 17/21	-42 17/21	206 4/21	35 4/21	47 4/21	156 4/21	154 4/21	152 4/21	150 4/21	46 4/21	48 4/21	50 4/21	52 4/21	54 4/21	147 4/21	157 4/21	-13 17/21	235 4/21	269 4/21	-92 17/21	2020	
283 4/21	-78 17/21	-44 17/21	208 4/21	25 4/21	180 4/21	178 4/21	176 4/21	174 4/21	172 4/21	24 4/21	26 4/21	28 4/21	30 4/21	32 4/21	34 4/21	169 4/21	-15 17/21	237 4/21	271 4/21	-90 17/21	2020	
281 4/21	-80 17/21	-46 17/21	- 17/21	11 4/21	9 4/21	7 4/21	5 4/21	3 4/21	1 4/21	196 4/21	197 4/21	199 4/21	201 4/21	203 4/21	205 4/21	207 4/21	-2 17/21	239 4/21	273 4/21	-88 17/21	2020	
279 4/21	-82 17/21	223 4/21	210 4/21	212 4/21	214 4/21	216 4/21	218 4/21	220 4/21	222 4/21	224 4/21	-35 17/21	-37 17/21	-39 17/21	-41 17/21	-43 17/21	-45 17/21	-47 17/21	-32 17/21	275 4/21	-86 17/21	2020	
277 4/21	257 4/21	242 4/21	244 4/21	246 4/21	248 4/21	250 4/21	252 4/21	254 4/21	256 4/21	258 4/21	-69 17/21	-71 17/21	-73 17/21	-75 17/21	-77 17/21	-79 17/21	-81 17/21	-83 17/21	-66 17/21	-84 17/21	2020	
297 4/21	-85 17/21	-87 17/21	-89 17/21	-91 17/21	-93 17/21	-95 17/21	-97 17/21	-99 17/21	-101 17/21	-103 17/21	300 4/21	302 4/21	304 4/21	306 4/21	308 4/21	310 4/21	312 4/21	314 4/21	316 4/21	-102 17/21	2020	
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= \frac{2020}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{21} & S_{13 \times 13} &:= \frac{26360}{21} = 2020 \times \frac{13}{21} \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= \frac{10100}{21} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{21} & S_{15 \times 15} &:= \frac{10100}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{15}{21} \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= \frac{2020}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{21} & S_{17 \times 17} &:= \frac{34340}{21} = 2020 \times \frac{17}{21} \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= \frac{6060}{7} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{21} & S_{19 \times 19} &:= \frac{38380}{21} = 2020 \times \frac{19}{21} \\
 S_{11 \times 11} &:= \frac{22220}{21} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{21} & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{21}{21}.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.20 Bordered Magic Square of Order 22

The bordered magic square of order 22 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

-129 15/22	322 7/22	-137 15/22	320 7/22	-135 15/22	318 7/22	-133 15/22	316 7/22	-131 15/22	314 7/22	-149 15/22	323 7/22	-127 15/22	310 7/22	-125 15/22	308 7/22	-123 15/22	306 7/22	-121 15/22	304 7/22	-119 15/22	312 7/22
-117 15/22	272 7/22	264 7/22	-81 15/22	266 7/22	-83 15/22	268 7/22	269 7/22	-86 15/22	-87 15/22	-98 15/22	-79 15/22	274 7/22	275 7/22	-92 15/22	277 7/22	-94 15/22	279 7/22	-96 15/22	281 7/22	-89 15/22	301 7/22
300 7/22	-78 15/22	236 7/22	-45 15/22	230 7/22	-47 15/22	232 7/22	-49 15/22	234 7/22	-51 15/22	245 7/22	-69 15/22	238 7/22	-55 15/22	240 7/22	-57 15/22	242 7/22	-59 15/22	244 7/22	-53 15/22	262 7/22	-116 15/22
-115 15/22	261 7/22	227 7/22	204 7/22	198 7/22	-15 15/22	200 7/22	201 7/22	-18 15/22	-19 15/22	-28 15/22	-13 15/22	206 7/22	207 7/22	-24 15/22	209 7/22	-26 15/22	211 7/22	-21 15/22	-43 15/22	-77 15/22	299 7/22
298 7/22	-76 15/22	-42 15/22	-12 15/22	176 7/22	12 7/22	172 7/22	10 7/22	174 7/22	8 7/22	183 7/22	-5 15/22	178 7/22	4 7/22	180 7/22	2 7/22	182 7/22	6 7/22	196 7/22	226 7/22	260 7/22	-114 15/22
-113 15/22	259 7/22	225 7/22	195 7/22	169 7/22	152 7/22	148 7/22	149 7/22	33 7/22	32 7/22	25 7/22	36 7/22	154 7/22	155 7/22	27 7/22	157 7/22	30 7/22	14 7/22	-11 15/22	-41 15/22	-75 15/22	297 7/22
296 7/22	-74 15/22	-40 15/22	-10 15/22	15 7/22	37 7/22	132 7/22	127 7/22	57 7/22	125 7/22	59 7/22	55 7/22	45 7/22	139 7/22	43 7/22	133 7/22	146 7/22	168 7/22	194 7/22	224 7/22	258 7/22	-112 15/22
-111 15/22	257 7/22	223 7/22	193 7/22	167 7/22	145 7/22	54 7/22	117 7/22	122 7/22	62 7/22	60 7/22	73 7/22	111 7/22	71 7/22	116 7/22	129 7/22	38 7/22	16 7/22	-9 15/22	-39 15/22	-73 15/22	295 7/22
294 7/22	-72 15/22	-38 15/22	-8 15/22	17 7/22	39 7/22	130 7/22	114 7/22	104 7/22	80 7/22	107 7/22	74 7/22	106 7/22	78 7/22	69 7/22	53 7/22	144 7/22	166 7/22	192 7/22	222 7/22	256 7/22	-110 15/22
-109 15/22	255 7/22	221 7/22	191 7/22	165 7/22	143 7/22	52 7/22	115 7/22	101 7/22	97 7/22	84 7/22	87 7/22	98 7/22	82 7/22	68 7/22	131 7/22	40 7/22	18 7/22	-7 15/22	-37 15/22	-71 15/22	293 7/22
292 7/22	-70 15/22	-36 15/22	-6 15/22	19 7/22	41 7/22	137 7/22	120 7/22	83 7/22	90 7/22	95 7/22	92 7/22	89 7/22	100 7/22	63 7/22	46 7/22	142 7/22	164 7/22	190 7/22	220 7/22	254 7/22	-108 15/22
302 7/22	-107 15/22	-44 15/22	-35 15/22	13 7/22	20 7/22	42 7/22	70 7/22	81 7/22	94 7/22	91 7/22	88 7/22	93 7/22	102 7/22	113 7/22	141 7/22	163 7/22	170 7/22	219 7/22	228 7/22	291 7/22	-118 15/22
324 7/22	-99 15/22	-62 15/22	-29 15/22	-0.6818182	24 7/22	134 7/22	65 7/22	75 7/22	85 7/22	96 7/22	99 7/22	86 7/22	108 7/22	118 7/22	49 7/22	159 7/22	184 7/22	213 7/22	246 7/22	283 7/22	-140 15/22
-141 15/22	284 7/22	247 7/22	214 7/22	185 7/22	160 7/22	48 7/22	64 7/22	105 7/22	103 7/22	76 7/22	109 7/22	77 7/22	79 7/22	119 7/22	135 7/22	23 7/22	-1 15/22	-30 15/22	-63 15/22	-100 15/22	325 7/22
326 7/22	-101 15/22	-64 15/22	-31 15/22	-2 15/22	22 7/22	136 7/22	67 7/22	61 7/22	121 7/22	123 7/22	110 7/22	72 7/22	112 7/22	66 7/22	47 7/22	161 7/22	186 7/22	215 7/22	248 7/22	285 7/22	-142 15/22
-143 15/22	286 7/22	249 7/22	216 7/22	187 7/22	162 7/22	50 7/22	56 7/22	126 7/22	58 7/22	124 7/22	128 7/22	138 7/22	44 7/22	140 7/22	51 7/22	21 7/22	-3 15/22	-32 15/22	-65 15/22	-102 15/22	327 7/22
328 7/22	-103 15/22	-66 15/22	-33 15/22	-4 15/22	153 7/22	35 7/22	34 7/22	150 7/22	151 7/22	158 7/22	147 7/22	29 7/22	28 7/22	156 7/22	26 7/22	31 7/22	188 7/22	217 7/22	250 7/22	287 7/22	-144 15/22
-145 15/22	288 7/22	251 7/22	218 7/22	177 7/22	171 7/22	11 7/22	173 7/22	9 7/22	175 7/22	7/22	189 7/22	5 7/22	179 7/22	3 7/22	181 7/22	1 7/22	7 7/22	-34 15/22	-67 15/22	-104 15/22	329 7/22
330 7/22	-105 15/22	-68 15/22	205 7/22	-14 15/22	199 7/22	-16 15/22	-17 15/22	202 7/22	203 7/22	212 7/22	197 7/22	-22 15/22	-23 15/22	208 7/22	-25 15/22	210 7/22	-27 15/22	-20 15/22	252 7/22	289 7/22	-146 15/22
-147 15/22	290 7/22	237 7/22	229 7/22	-46 15/22	231 7/22	-48 15/22	233 7/22	-50 15/22	235 7/22	-61 15/22	253 7/22	-54 15/22	239 7/22	-56 15/22	241 7/22	-58 15/22	243 7/22	-60 15/22	-52 15/22	-106 15/22	331 7/22
332 7/22	273 7/22	-80 15/22	265 7/22	-82 15/22	267 7/22	-84 15/22	-85 15/22	270 7/22	271 7/22	282 7/22	263 7/22	-90 15/22	-91 15/22	276 7/22	-93 15/22	278 7/22	-95 15/22	280 7/22	-97 15/22	-88 15/22	-148 15/22
-128 15/22	-138 15/22	321 7/22	-136 15/22	319 7/22	-134 15/22	317 7/22	-132 15/22	315 7/22	-130 15/22	333 7/22	-139 15/22	311 7/22	-126 15/22	309 7/22	-124 15/22	307 7/22	-122 15/22	305 7/22	-120 15/22	303 7/22	313 7/22
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4039}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{4}{22}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6060}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{6}{22}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8080}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{22}$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10100}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{22}$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12120}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{22}$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14140}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{13}{22}$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{16160}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{15}{22}$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := \frac{18180}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{17}{22}$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{20200}{11} = 2020 \times \frac{19}{22}$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{21}{22}$$

2.21 Bordered Magic Square of Order 23

The bordered magic square of order 23 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

2020

330 19/23	-134 4/23	-136 4/23	-138 4/23	-140 4/23	-142 4/23	-144 4/23	-146 4/23	-148 4/23	-150 4/23	-152 4/23	-154 4/23	333 19/23	335 19/23	337 19/23	339 19/23	341 19/23	343 19/23	345 19/23	347 19/23	349 19/23	351 19/23	-153 4/23	2020	
308 19/23	286 19/23	269 19/23	271 19/23	273 19/23	275 19/23	277 19/23	279 19/23	281 19/23	283 19/23	285 19/23	287 19/23	-116 4/23	-118 4/23	-120 4/23	-122 4/23	-124 4/23	-126 4/23	-128 4/23	-130 4/23	-132 4/23	-113 4/23	-133 4/23	2020	
310 19/23	-131 4/23	250 19/23	-58 4/23	-60 4/23	-62 4/23	-64 4/23	-66 4/23	-68 4/23	-70 4/23	-72 4/23	-74 4/23	253 19/23	255 19/23	257 19/23	259 19/23	261 19/23	263 19/23	265 19/23	267 19/23	-73 4/23	306 19/23	-135 4/23	2020	
312 19/23	-129 4/23	232 19/23	216 19/23	-26 4/23	-28 4/23	-30 4/23	-32 4/23	-34 4/23	-36 4/23	-38 4/23	-40 4/23	219 19/23	221 19/23	223 19/23	225 19/23	227 19/23	229 19/23	231 19/23	-39 4/23	-57 4/23	304 19/23	-137 4/23	2020	
314 19/23	-127 4/23	234 19/23	200 19/23	186 19/23	172 19/23	174 19/23	176 19/23	178 19/23	180 19/23	182 19/23	-12 4/23	-13 4/23	-15 4/23	-17 4/23	-19 4/23	-21 4/23	-23 4/23	184 19/23	-25 4/23	-59 4/23	302 19/23	-139 4/23	2020	
316 19/23	-125 4/23	236 19/23	202 19/23	1 19/23	14 19/23	3 19/23	5 19/23	7 19/23	9 19/23	11 19/23	159 19/23	157 19/23	155 19/23	153 19/23	151 19/23	149 19/23	158 19/23	173 19/23	-27 4/23	-61 4/23	300 19/23	-141 4/23	2020	
318 19/23	-123 4/23	238 19/23	204 19/23	-0.173913	170 19/23	36 19/23	27 19/23	29 19/23	31 19/23	33 19/23	137 19/23	135 19/23	133 19/23	131 19/23	129 19/23	136 19/23	4 19/23	175 19/23	-29 4/23	-63 4/23	298 19/23	-143 4/23	2020	
320 19/23	-121 4/23	240 19/23	206 19/23	-2 4/23	168 19/23	146 19/23	118 19/23	48 19/23	50 19/23	52 19/23	53 19/23	116 19/23	114 19/23	112 19/23	120 19/23	28 19/23	6 19/23	177 19/23	-31 4/23	-65 4/23	296 19/23	-145 4/23	2020	
322 19/23	-119 4/23	242 19/23	208 19/23	-4 4/23	166 19/23	144 19/23	113 19/23	104 19/23	64 19/23	66 19/23	67 19/23	102 19/23	100 19/23	106 19/23	61 19/23	30 19/23	8 19/23	179 19/23	-33 4/23	-67 4/23	294 19/23	-147 4/23	2020	
324 19/23	-117 4/23	244 19/23	210 19/23	-6 4/23	164 19/23	142 19/23	115 19/23	101 19/23	96 19/23	92 19/23	77 19/23	76 19/23	94 19/23	73 19/23	59 19/23	32 19/23	10 19/23	181 19/23	-35 4/23	-69 4/23	292 19/23	-149 4/23	2020	
326 19/23	-115 4/23	246 19/23	212 19/23	-8 4/23	162 19/23	140 19/23	117 19/23	103 19/23	81 19/23	84 19/23	89 19/23	88 19/23	93 19/23	71 19/23	57 19/23	34 19/23	12 19/23	183 19/23	-37 4/23	-71 4/23	290 19/23	-151 4/23	2020	
-156 4/23	-114 4/23	-76 4/23	-42 4/23	-10 4/23	161 19/23	139 19/23	119 19/23	105 19/23	79 19/23	91 19/23	87 19/23	83 19/23	95 19/23	69 19/23	55 19/23	35 19/23	13 19/23	185 19/23	217 19/23	251 19/23	289 19/23	331 19/23	2020	
-157 4/23	284 19/23	-77 4/23	-43 4/23	189 19/23	18 19/23	40 19/23	51 19/23	65 19/23	99 19/23	86 19/23	85 19/23	90 19/23	75 19/23	109 19/23	123 19/23	134 19/23	156 19/23	-14 4/23	218 19/23	252 19/23	-109 4/23	332 19/23	2020	
-159 4/23	282 19/23	-79 4/23	-45 4/23	191 19/23	20 19/23	42 19/23	49 19/23	63 19/23	80 19/23	82 19/23	97 19/23	98 19/23	78 19/23	111 19/23	125 19/23	132 19/23	154 19/23	-16 4/23	220 19/23	254 19/23	-107 4/23	334 19/23	2020	
-161 4/23	280 19/23	-81 4/23	-47 4/23	193 19/23	22 19/23	44 19/23	47 19/23	68 19/23	110 19/23	108 19/23	107 19/23	72 19/23	74 19/23	70 19/23	127 19/23	130 19/23	152 19/23	-18 4/23	222 19/23	256 19/23	-105 4/23	336 19/23	2020	
-163 4/23	278 19/23	-83 4/23	-49 4/23	195 19/23	24 19/23	46 19/23	54 19/23	126 19/23	124 19/23	122 19/23	121 19/23	58 19/23	60 19/23	62 19/23	56 19/23	128 19/23	150 19/23	-20 4/23	224 19/23	258 19/23	-103 4/23	338 19/23	2020	
-165 4/23	276 19/23	-85 4/23	-51 4/23	197 19/23	26 19/23	38 19/23	147 19/23	145 19/23	143 19/23	141 19/23	37 19/23	39 19/23	41 19/23	43 19/23	45 19/23	138 19/23	148 19/23	-22 4/23	226 19/23	260 19/23	-101 4/23	340 19/23	2020	
-167 4/23	274 19/23	-87 4/23	-53 4/23	199 19/23	16 19/23	171 19/23	169 19/23	167 19/23	165 19/23	163 19/23	15 19/23	17 19/23	19 19/23	21 19/23	23 19/23	25 19/23	160 19/23	-24 4/23	228 19/23	262 19/23	-99 4/23	342 19/23	2020	
-169 4/23	272 19/23	-89 4/23	-55 4/23	-9 4/23	2 19/23	19 23	-1 4/23	-3 4/23	-5 4/23	-7 4/23	187 19/23	188 19/23	190 19/23	192 19/23	194 19/23	196 19/23	198 19/23	-11 4/23	230 19/23	264 19/23	-97 4/23	344 19/23	2020	
-171 4/23	270 19/23	-91 4/23	214 19/23	201 19/23	203 19/23	205 19/23	207 19/23	209 19/23	211 19/23	213 19/23	215 19/23	-44 4/23	-46 4/23	-48 4/23	-50 4/23	-52 4/23	-54 4/23	-56 4/23	-41 4/23	266 19/23	-95 4/23	346 19/23	2020	
-173 4/23	268 19/23	248 19/23	233 19/23	235 19/23	237 19/23	239 19/23	241 19/23	243 19/23	245 19/23	247 19/23	249 19/23	-78 4/23	-80 4/23	-82 4/23	-84 4/23	-86 4/23	-88 4/23	-90 4/23	-92 4/23	-75 4/23	-93 4/23	348 19/23	2020	
-175 4/23	288 19/23	-94 4/23	-96 4/23	-98 4/23	-100 4/23	-102 4/23	-104 4/23	-106 4/23	-108 4/23	-110 4/23	-112 4/23	291 19/23	293 19/23	295 19/23	297 19/23	299 19/23	301 19/23	303 19/23	305 19/23	307 19/23	-111 4/23	350 19/23	2020	
328 19/23	309 19/23	311 19/23	313 19/23	315 19/23	317 19/23	319 19/23	321 19/23	323 19/23	325 19/23	327 19/23	329 19/23	-158 4/23	-160 4/23	-162 4/23	-164 4/23	-166 4/23	-168 4/23	-170 4/23	-172 4/23	-174 4/23	-176 4/23	-155 4/23	2020	
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{6060}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{3}{23}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10100}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{5}{23}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{14140}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{7}{23}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18180}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{9}{23}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{22220}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{11}{23}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{26260}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{13}{23}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30300}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{15}{23}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{34340}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{17}{23}$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := \frac{38380}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{19}{23}$$

$$S_{21 \times 21} := \frac{42420}{23} = 2020 \times \frac{21}{23}$$

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{23}{23}$$

2.22 Bordered Magic Square of Order 24

The bordered magic square of order 24 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

349 2/3	-170 1/3	339 2/3	-172 1/3	341 2/3	-174 1/3	343 2/3	-176 1/3	-177 1/3	346 2/3	347 2/3	360 2/3	337 2/3	-182 1/3	-183 1/3	352 2/3	-185 1/3	354 2/3	-187 1/3	356 2/3	-189 1/3	358 2/3	-191 1/3	-180 1/3	2020	
370 2/3	-137 1/3	314 2/3	-145 1/3	312 2/3	-143 1/3	310 2/3	-141 1/3	308 2/3	-139 1/3	306 2/3	-157 1/3	315 2/3	-135 1/3	302 2/3	-133 1/3	300 2/3	-131 1/3	298 2/3	-129 1/3	296 2/3	-127 1/3	304 2/3	-202 1/3		2020
-201 1/3	-125 1/3	264 2/3	256 2/3	-89 1/3	258 2/3	-91 1/3	260 2/3	261 2/3	-94 1/3	-95 1/3	-106 1/3	-87 1/3	266 2/3	267 2/3	-100 1/3	269 2/3	-102 1/3	271 2/3	-104 1/3	273 2/3	-97 1/3	293 2/3	369 2/3		2020
368 2/3	292 2/3	-86 1/3	228 2/3	-53 1/3	222 2/3	-55 1/3	224 2/3	-57 1/3	226 2/3	-59 1/3	237 2/3	-77 1/3	230 2/3	-63 1/3	232 2/3	-65 1/3	234 2/3	-67 1/3	236 2/3	-61 1/3	254 2/3	-124 1/3	-200 1/3		2020
-199 1/3	-123 1/3	253 2/3	219 2/3	196 2/3	190 2/3	-23 1/3	192 2/3	193 2/3	-26 1/3	-27 1/3	-36 1/3	-21 1/3	198 2/3	199 2/3	-32 1/3	201 2/3	-34 1/3	203 2/3	-29 1/3	-51 1/3	-85 1/3	291 2/3	367 2/3		2020
366 2/3	290 2/3	-84 1/3	-50 1/3	-20 1/3	168 2/3	4 2/3	164 2/3	2 2/3	166 2/3	2/3	175 2/3	-13 1/3	170 2/3	-3 1/3	172 2/3	-5 1/3	174 2/3	-1 1/3	188 2/3	218 2/3	252 2/3	-122 1/3	-198 1/3		2020
-197 1/3	-121 1/3	251 2/3	217 2/3	187 2/3	161 2/3	144 2/3	140 2/3	141 2/3	25 2/3	24 2/3	17 2/3	28 2/3	146 2/3	147 2/3	19 2/3	149 2/3	22 2/3	6 2/3	-19 1/3	-49 1/3	-83 1/3	289 2/3	365 2/3		2020
364 2/3	288 2/3	-82 1/3	-48 1/3	-18 1/3	7 2/3	29 2/3	124 2/3	119 2/3	49 2/3	117 2/3	51 2/3	47 2/3	37 2/3	131 2/3	35 2/3	125 2/3	138 2/3	160 2/3	186 2/3	216 2/3	250 2/3	-120 1/3	-196 1/3		2020
-195 1/3	-119 1/3	249 2/3	215 2/3	185 2/3	159 2/3	137 2/3	46 2/3	109 2/3	114 2/3	54 2/3	52 2/3	65 2/3	103 2/3	63 2/3	108 2/3	121 2/3	30 2/3	8 2/3	-17 1/3	-47 1/3	-81 1/3	287 2/3	363 2/3		2020
362 2/3	286 2/3	-80 1/3	-46 1/3	-16 1/3	9 2/3	31 2/3	122 2/3	106 2/3	96 2/3	72 2/3	99 2/3	66 2/3	98 2/3	70 2/3	61 2/3	45 2/3	136 2/3	158 2/3	184 2/3	214 2/3	248 2/3	-118 1/3	-194 1/3		2020
-193 1/3	-117 1/3	247 2/3	213 2/3	183 2/3	157 2/3	135 2/3	44 2/3	107 2/3	93 2/3	89 2/3	76 2/3	79 2/3	90 2/3	74 2/3	60 2/3	123 2/3	32 2/3	10 2/3	-15 1/3	-45 1/3	-79 1/3	285 2/3	361 2/3		2020
-203 1/3	284 2/3	-78 1/3	-44 1/3	-14 1/3	11 2/3	33 2/3	129 2/3	112 2/3	75 2/3	82 2/3	87 2/3	84 2/3	81 2/3	92 2/3	55 2/3	38 2/3	134 2/3	156 2/3	182 2/3	212 2/3	246 2/3	-116 1/3	-192 1/3		2020
-158 1/3	294 2/3	-115 1/3	-52 1/3	-43 1/3	5 2/3	12 2/3	34 2/3	62 2/3	73 2/3	86 2/3	83 2/3	80 2/3	85 2/3	94 2/3	105 2/3	133 2/3	155 2/3	162 2/3	211 2/3	220 2/3	283 2/3	-126 1/3	-162 1/3		2020
327 2/3	316 2/3	-107 1/3	-70 1/3	-37 1/3	-8 1/3	16 2/3	126 2/3	57 2/3	67 2/3	77 2/3	88 2/3	91 2/3	78 2/3	100 2/3	110 2/3	41 2/3	151 2/3	176 2/3	205 2/3	238 2/3	275 2/3	-148 1/3	-159 1/3		2020
-160 1/3	-149 1/3	276 2/3	239 2/3	206 2/3	177 2/3	152 2/3	40 2/3	56 2/3	97 2/3	95 2/3	68 2/3	101 2/3	69 2/3	71 2/3	111 2/3	127 2/3	15 2/3	-9 1/3	-38 1/3	-71 1/3	-108 1/3	317 2/3	328 2/3		2020
329 2/3	318 2/3	-109 1/3	-72 1/3	-39 1/3	-10 1/3	14 2/3	128 2/3	59 2/3	53 2/3	113 2/3	115 2/3	102 2/3	64 2/3	104 2/3	58 2/3	39 2/3	153 2/3	178 2/3	207 2/3	240 2/3	277 2/3	-150 1/3	-161 1/3		2020
-162 1/3	-151 1/3	278 2/3	241 2/3	208 2/3	179 2/3	154 2/3	42 2/3	48 2/3	118 2/3	50 2/3	116 2/3	120 2/3	130 2/3	36 2/3	132 2/3	43 2/3	13 2/3	-11 1/3	-40 1/3	-73 1/3	-110 1/3	319 2/3	330 2/3		2020
331 2/3	320 2/3	-111 1/3	-74 1/3	-41 1/3	-12 1/3	145 2/3	27 2/3	26 2/3	142 2/3	143 2/3	150 2/3	139 2/3	21 2/3	20 2/3	148 2/3	18 2/3	23 2/3	180 2/3	209 2/3	242 2/3	279 2/3	-152 1/3	-163 1/3		2020
-164 1/3	-153 1/3	280 2/3	243 2/3	210 2/3	169 2/3	163 2/3	3 2/3	165 2/3	1 2/3	167 2/3	-7 1/3	181 2/3	-2 1/3	171 2/3	-4 1/3	173 2/3	-6 1/3	-1 1/3	-42 1/3	-75 1/3	-112 1/3	321 2/3	332 2/3		2020
333 2/3	322 2/3	-113 1/3	-76 1/3	197 2/3	-22 1/3	191 2/3	-24 1/3	-25 1/3	194 2/3	195 2/3	204 2/3	189 2/3	-30 1/3	-31 1/3	200 2/3	-33 1/3	202 2/3	-35 1/3	-28 1/3	244 2/3	281 2/3	-154 1/3	-165 1/3		2020
-166 1/3	-155 1/3	282 2/3	229 2/3	221 2/3	-54 1/3	223 2/3	-56 1/3	225 2/3	-58 1/3	227 2/3	-69 1/3	245 2/3	-62 1/3	231 2/3	-64 1/3	233 2/3	-66 1/3	235 2/3	-68 1/3	-60 1/3	-114 1/3	323 2/3	334 2/3		2020
335 2/3	324 2/3	265 2/3	-88 1/3	257 2/3	-90 1/3	259 2/3	-92 1/3	-93 1/3	262 2/3	263 2/3	274 2/3	255 2/3	-98 1/3	-99 1/3	268 2/3	-101 1/3	270 2/3	-103 1/3	272 2/3	-105 1/3	-96 1/3	-156 1/3	-167 1/3		2020
-168 1/3	-136 1/3	-146 1/3	313 2/3	-144 1/3	311 2/3	-142 1/3	309 2/3	-140 1/3	307 2/3	-138 1/3	325 2/3	-147 1/3	303 2/3	-134 1/3	301 2/3	-132 1/3	299 2/3	-130 1/3	297 2/3	-128 1/3	295 2/3	305 2/3	336 2/3		2020
348 2/3	338 2/3	-171 1/3	340 2/3	-173 1/3	342 2/3	-175 1/3	344 2/3	345 2/3	-178 1/3	-179 1/3	-192 1/3	-169 1/3	350 2/3	351 2/3	-184 1/3	353 2/3	-186 1/3	355 2/3	-188 1/3	357 2/3	-190 1/3	359 2/3	-181 1/3		2020
2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{1010}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{4}{24} & S_{12 \times 12} := 1010 = 2020 \times \frac{12}{21} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} := 505 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{21} & S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{3535}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{14}{24} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{2020}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{6}{24} & S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{4040}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{16}{24} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{2525}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{10}{24} & S_{18 \times 18} := 1515 = 2020 \times \frac{18}{21} \\
 & S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{5050}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{20}{24} \\
 & S_{22 \times 22} := \frac{5555}{3} = 2020 \times \frac{22}{24} \\
 & S_{24 \times 24} := 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{24}{24}
 \end{array}$$

2.23 Bordered Magic Square of Order 25

The bordered magic square of order 23 for the magic sum 2020 is given by

-206.2	392.8	390.8	388.8	386.8	384.8	382.8	380.8	378.8	376.8	374.8	372.8	-207.2	-205.2	-203.2	-201.2	-199.2	-197.2	-195.2	-193.2	-191.2	-189.2	-187.2	-185.2	369.8	2020
-184.2	323.8	-141.2	-143.2	-145.2	-147.2	-149.2	-151.2	-153.2	-155.2	-157.2	-159.2	-161.2	326.8	328.8	330.8	332.8	334.8	336.8	338.8	340.8	342.8	344.8	-160.2	345.8	2020
-186.2	301.8	279.8	262.8	264.8	266.8	268.8	270.8	272.8	274.8	276.8	278.8	280.8	-123.2	-125.2	-127.2	-129.2	-131.2	-133.2	-135.2	-137.2	-139.2	-140.2	347.8	2020	
-188.2	303.8	-138.2	243.8	-65.2	-67.2	-69.2	-71.2	-73.2	-75.2	-77.2	-79.2	-81.2	246.8	248.8	250.8	252.8	254.8	256.8	258.8	260.8	-80.2	299.8	-142.2	349.8	2020
-190.2	305.8	-136.2	225.8	209.8	-33.2	-35.2	-37.2	-39.2	-41.2	-43.2	-45.2	-47.2	212.8	214.8	216.8	218.8	220.8	222.8	224.8	-46.2	-64.2	297.8	-144.2	351.8	2020
-192.2	307.8	-134.2	227.8	193.8	179.8	165.8	167.8	169.8	171.8	173.8	175.8	-19.2	-20.2	-22.2	-24.2	-26.2	-28.2	-30.2	177.8	-32.2	-66.2	295.8	-146.2	353.8	2020
-194.2	309.8	-132.2	229.8	195.8	-5.2	7.8	-3.2	-1.2	0.8	2.8	4.8	152.8	150.8	148.8	146.8	144.8	142.8	151.8	166.8	-34.2	-68.2	293.8	-148.2	355.8	2020
-196.2	311.8	-130.2	231.8	197.8	-7.2	163.8	29.8	20.8	22.8	24.8	26.8	130.8	128.8	126.8	124.8	122.8	129.8	-2.2	168.8	-36.2	-70.2	291.8	-150.2	357.8	2020
-198.2	313.8	-128.2	233.8	199.8	-9.2	161.8	139.8	111.8	41.8	43.8	45.8	46.8	109.8	107.8	105.8	113.8	21.8	-0.2	170.8	-38.2	-72.2	289.8	-152.2	359.8	2020
-200.2	315.8	-126.2	235.8	201.8	-11.2	159.8	137.8	106.8	97.8	57.8	59.8	60.8	95.8	93.8	99.8	54.8	23.8	1.8	172.8	-40.2	-74.2	287.8	-154.2	361.8	2020
-202.2	317.8	-124.2	237.8	203.8	-13.2	157.8	135.8	108.8	94.8	89.8	85.8	70.8	69.8	87.8	66.8	52.8	25.8	3.8	174.8	-42.2	-76.2	285.8	-156.2	363.8	2020
-204.2	319.8	-122.2	239.8	205.8	-15.2	155.8	133.8	110.8	96.8	74.8	77.8	82.8	81.8	86.8	64.8	50.8	27.8	5.8	176.8	-44.2	-78.2	283.8	-158.2	365.8	2020
370.8	-163.2	-121.2	-83.2	-49.2	-17.2	154.8	132.8	112.8	98.8	72.8	84.8	80.8	76.8	88.8	62.8	48.8	28.8	6.8	178.8	210.8	244.8	282.8	324.8	-209.2	2020
371.8	-164.2	277.8	-84.2	-50.2	182.8	11.8	33.8	44.8	58.8	92.8	79.8	78.8	83.8	68.8	102.8	116.8	127.8	149.8	-21.2	211.8	245.8	-116.2	325.8	-210.2	2020
373.8	-166.2	275.8	-86.2	-52.2	184.8	13.8	35.8	42.8	56.8	73.8	75.8	90.8	91.8	71.8	104.8	118.8	125.8	147.8	-23.2	213.8	247.8	-114.2	327.8	-212.2	2020
375.8	-168.2	273.8	-88.2	-54.2	186.8	15.8	37.8	40.8	61.8	103.8	101.8	100.8	65.8	67.8	63.8	120.8	123.8	145.8	-25.2	215.8	249.8	-112.2	329.8	-214.2	2020
377.8	-170.2	271.8	-90.2	-56.2	188.8	17.8	39.8	47.8	119.8	117.8	115.8	114.8	51.8	53.8	55.8	49.8	121.8	143.8	-27.2	217.8	251.8	-110.2	331.8	-216.2	2020
379.8	-172.2	269.8	-92.2	-58.2	190.8	19.8	31.8	140.8	138.8	136.8	134.8	30.8	32.8	34.8	36.8	38.8	131.8	141.8	-29.2	219.8	253.8	-108.2	333.8	-218.2	2020
381.8	-174.2	267.8	-94.2	-60.2	192.8	9.8	164.8	162.8	160.8	158.8	156.8	8.8	10.8	12.8	14.8	16.8	18.8	153.8	-31.2	221.8	255.8	-106.2	335.8	-220.2	2020
383.8	-176.2	265.8	-96.2	-62.2	194.8	-4.2	-6.2	-8.2	-10.2	-12.2	-14.2	180.8	181.8	183.8	185.8	187.8	189.8	191.8	-18.2	223.8	257.8	-104.2	337.8	-222.2	2020
385.8	-178.2	263.8	-98.2	207.8	194.8	196.8	198.8	200.8	202.8	204.8	206.8	208.8	-51.2	-53.2	-55.2	-57.2	-59.2	-61.2	-63.2	-48.2	259.8	-102.2	339.8	-224.2	2020
387.8	-180.2	261.8	241.8	226.8	228.8	230.8	232.8	234.8	236.8	238.8	240.8	242.8	-85.2	-87.2	-89.2	-91.2	-93.2	-95.2	-97.2	-99.2	-82.2	-100.2	341.8	-226.2	2020
389.8	-182.2	281.8	-101.2	-103.2	-105.2	-107.2	-109.2	-111.2	-113.2	-115.2	-117.2	-119.2	284.8	286.8	288.8	290.8	292.8	294.8	296.8	298.8	300.8	-118.2	343.8	-228.2	2020
391.8	321.8	302.8	304.8	306.8	308.8	310.8	312.8	314.8	316.8	318.8	320.8	322.8	-165.2	-167.2	-169.2	-171.2	-173.2	-175.2	-177.2	-179.2	-181.2	-183.2	-162.2	-230.2	2020
-208.2	-231.2	-229.2	-227.2	-225.2	-223.2	-221.2	-219.2	-217.2	-215.2	-213.2	-211.2	368.8	366.8	364.8	362.8	360.8	358.8	356.8	354.8	352.8	350.8	348.8	346.8	367.8	2020

The sub-magic square sums are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{3 \times 3} &:= 242.4 = 2020 \times \frac{3}{25} & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 1212 = 2020 \times \frac{15}{25} \\ S_{5 \times 5} &:= 404 = 2020 \times \frac{5}{25} & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 1373.6 = 2020 \times \frac{17}{25} \\ S_{7 \times 7} &:= 565.6 = 2020 \times \frac{7}{25} & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 1535.2 = 2020 \times \frac{19}{25} \\ S_{9 \times 9} &:= 727.2 = 2020 \times \frac{9}{25} & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 1696.8 = 2020 \times \frac{21}{25} \\ S_{11 \times 11} &:= 888.8 = 2020 \times \frac{11}{25} & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 1858.4 = 2020 \times \frac{23}{25} \\ S_{13 \times 13} &:= 1050.4 = 2020 \times \frac{13}{25} & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 2020 = 2020 \times \frac{25}{25}. \end{aligned}$$

3 Final Result

Observing the examples above, we get the following results for general case:

Result 3.1. *The sub-magic sums of bordered magic square are given by*

$$S_{k \times k} := 2020 \times \frac{k}{m},$$

where k is the order each *sub-magic square* and m is the order of *bordered magic squares*.

For example, let's consider $k=25$, then

$$S_{k \times k} := 2020 \times \frac{k}{25},$$

where $k = 3, 5, 7 \dots 23, 25$.

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